

System of Creative Thinking Skills Formation in Students

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Abstract. *In this article, students can develop creative thinking skills, creative thinking skills that help them make confident decisions and quickly acquire new knowledge for success, improve people's lives through new ideas, connect people and opportunities, or there is talk of harmonizing.*

Key words: *Creativity, creative thinking, new technology, skills, innovation, advanced thinking.*

Creative approaches and achievements have advanced human civilization worldwide in fields ranging from science and technology to philosophy, the arts, and the humanities. So, creative thinking is more than just coming up with random ideas. It is a real skill based on knowledge and experience that allows a person to achieve a better result in sometimes difficult conditions. Societies and organizations around the world increasingly need innovative knowledge and creativity to solve problems Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, which in turn reinforces the importance of teamwork innovation and creative thinking[1].

The main task of education is to form the skills that the student will need today and in the future to lead a successful life in society. Creative thinking is an important skill for today's youth. These skills help them adapt to a world that is constantly and rapidly changing, requiring workers with "21st century" skills that go beyond basic literacy. In general, today's student is expected to work in fields that do not even exist now, to solve new problems using new technologies. Formation of creative thinking skills in students allows them to solve increasingly complex local and global problems through an unusual approach[2].

Also, creative thinking helps students interpret events, experiences, and behaviors in new and personally meaningful ways.

supports through The learner's imagination and curiosity come into play in the learning process: creative thinking thus becomes a means of mutual agreement, even in the context of predetermined educational goals. In order to increase student motivation and interest in school, it is necessary to introduce new forms of education that take into account the creative potential and enthusiasm of all students. It can help students who are not particularly interested in the educational process, and it helps them express their opinions and develop their potential [3].

Like any other skill, creative thinking can be developed through a hands-on approach. Some teachers may feel that developing students' creative thinking comes at the expense of other subjects in the curriculum. In fact, students can think creatively in all subjects. Creative thinking can be developed through approaches that encourage exploration and invention rather than blind memorization during instructional classes.

Teachers should be able to distinguish creative thinking, know the conditions suitable for such thinking, and know how to help students to think more creatively. A better understanding of how creative thinking occurs, in turn, helps teachers understand that creative ideas in students need a certain amount of time to "incubate" during the educational process [4].

Creativity and innovation are often cited as key skills for career success and life success around the world today. Innovation is a decisive force for an organization's performance and survival in the market. Changes in technology, globalization and increased competition create an environment where creativity and innovation are needed to cope with situational and economic pressures and frequent changes. Therefore, designers and developers of organizational systems must innovate almost continuously to adapt the organization to such changes[5].

Scientific interest in creativity is found in a number of disciplines, primarily psychology, business research, and cognitive science. However, it can also be found in education, humanities and theology, social sciences, engineering, technology, and mathematics.

These disciplines cover the relationship between creativity and general intelligence, personality type, mental and spiritual processes, mental health, and artificial intelligence. The potential to develop creativity through education, training, leadership and organizational practices, the determinants of how creativity is valued and perceived, the development of creativity for the national economic interest and the use of creative resources to improve teaching and learning effectiveness.

Creativity is the skill of creativity, creative approach. All the successful people in the world, from businessmen to artists, have stood out because of this skill. Creativity means imagining something that is still unclear in an unconventional, original way. For example, when the artist and sculptor Michelangelo was asked how he created his works so perfectly and perfectly, he replied: "Every time I enter into the creative process, I see characters trapped in a huge marble and I want to free them. I want." Creative thinking develops ideas, and ideas inspire change.

Creative thinking means improving people's lives through new ideas, connecting people and opportunities, that is, bringing them into harmony. If you ask successful people the secret of their success, they will tell you that they just focused on something that others didn't. In fact, they were able to consolidate the accumulated experience and connect knowledge. They focused on failure more than others. The only difference between leaders in their field and those who follow them is innovation, that is, forward thinking. You can't innovate without failing. Creativity is thinking of new ideas, innovation is the implementation of advanced work. To do this, you must not be afraid of failure.

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